

A Framework for Dynamic Risk Assessment in Subsurface Excavation Projects

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Unexpected ground conditions force the designers of underground construction projects to take on unnecessary levels of risk and expense when excavating. Rigid contractual agreements exacerbate this issue by impeding the sensible modification of design plans in response to newly collected geotechnical data. Together, inflexible contractual obligations and the lack of real-time risk assessment in excavation projects result in an inability to effectively adapt design plans to unexpected ground conditions. Here we propose a framework for dynamic risk assessment in excavation projects, utilizing dynamic geological modeling techniques to automatically update subsurface models following the collection of new data. Lithographic modeling techniques provide a straightforward method to extrapolate information from preliminary borehole measurements to construct an initial 3-D geological model, while geostatistical modeling techniques allow for relatively easy updating of the predicted models following the addition of a wide variety of newly collected data (e.g. geophysical, remote sensing, in-situ observations). An additional benefit of using geostatistical techniques is the ability to quantify uncertainty in our model; subsurface model uncertainty plays a large role in quantifying risk, just as potentially adverse ground conditions do. Combining these two modeling techniques, a dynamic geological model is obtained which complies with initial lithographic interpretations while accounting for changes in ground conditions illuminated by newly collected data. This model also highlights where, according to collected data, we are uncertain about predicted ground conditions, allowing for a more realistic risk assessment. Additional features of the dynamic risk assessment framework will include a GIS-based data aggregation system to incorporate data into the geological model in real-time, as well as modifications to the contractual system to allow for adaptation of initial design plans to dynamically unfolding ground conditions.